

THE NEED TO ATTRACT INVESTMENTS IN INNOVATION PROCESSES IN AGRICULTURE

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Abstract: New approaches have been developed by studying the history of agricultural development and contemporary challenges. Historically, the focus has been on public sector research through centralized research systems, but these approaches are now seen as insufficient. The concept of innovation systems offers new strategies for the effective application of new knowledge and ensuring sustainable development. The need for the integration of agriculture into global value chains and the application of new technologies is increasing. Focusing on innovation systems helps countries create new opportunities and adapt to changing conditions.

Keywords: agriculture, innovation systems, centralized systems, diversification, global value chains, private enterprises, technologies, knowledge integration, sustainable development.

INTRODUCTION

Agricultural development depends to a large extent on how knowledge is successfully generated and applied. Investment in knowledge, especially in the form of science and technology, has been an important and ongoing part of national strategies to promote sustainable and equitable agricultural development. While many of these investments have been highly successful, the process of generating and using knowledge has also changed as the agricultural context has changed rapidly and sometimes dramatically. It is clear that traditional agricultural science and technology investments, such as research and extension, while necessary, are not sufficient to drive agricultural innovation.

Literature review

When analyzing the literature on the topic, it is appropriate to cite the works of the following scholars:

Technical change and innovation in the sector have become more interactive processes, which can be controlled by different actors.

Five changes that have occurred in the development of agriculture require studying how innovation occurs in the agricultural sector.

Today, markets, not products, increasingly drive agricultural development. For much of the 20th century, major advances in agricultural development were driven by productivity gains in staple food crops, but this is changing. With falling food prices and rising urban incomes, profit-making strategies are shifting to diversifying agriculture and increasing the value added of agricultural production. [1], [3], [4]. Centralized government research systems are struggling to keep up with this trend, compared to the past. Rapid advances in information and communication technology, especially the Internet and other technologies, have dramatically changed the way knowledge is accessed. [2]

In our opinion, the following are relevant in this context:

First, the production, trade and consumption environment for agricultural products is developing in increasingly dynamic and unpredictable directions. If farmers are to adapt and compete in modern agriculture, they must constantly innovate. The driving forces for innovation are:

- 1) the emergence of disease problems in the industry;
- 2) changes in competition in local markets;
- 3) changes in trade regulations and the need for constant updating to comply with them;
- 4) changing technological paradigms such as biotechnology and information technology and the opportunities they offer.

Second, research and technology are increasingly being produced and applied by the private sector. Private enterprises develop and supply many of the technologies that farmers use (e.g., seeds, fertilizers, pesticides, and machinery).

Third, the information and communication technology and biotechnology revolutions have shown that many innovations in the agricultural sector—such as geographic information systems, global positioning systems, and bioinformatics—are based on knowledge created in other fields. The question of how to use new knowledge is becoming as important as how to create and disseminate new knowledge.

Fourth, the knowledge structure of the agricultural sector is changing significantly in many countries. Thirty years ago, there was a shortage of innovation and expertise in the sector. In this context, it made sense to create a significant part of the intellectual resources for the creation of new technologies, mainly in national agricultural research institutes. Since then, levels of general and agricultural education have increased in many countries. In rural communities, the private sector and non-governmental organizations (NGOs) are increasingly collaborating with experienced and knowledgeable individuals to generate new ideas or respond to changing conditions.

Fifth, agricultural development is taking place in an increasingly globalized environment. This change is influenced by the five changes mentioned earlier: the domestic market is no longer the only market that determines demand; environmental and health issues cross national borders; knowledge from abroad can be more important than domestic knowledge; and information and communication technologies (ICTs) enable the dissemination of information through international networks. Globalization leads to the fact that quality standards are increasingly determined by international markets and that small sectors are suddenly faced with a large potential demand. This increases the stakes in agricultural development: for

example, success in exporting non-traditional products can be much greater than in a limited world, but failure to adapt to new conditions can lead to failure and the rapid disappearance of traditional outlets.

Most agricultural production is increasingly integrated into value chains, with upstream (marketing) and downstream (input supply) links. Supply chains can become longer with the impact of urban markets; as a result, shelf life, processing requirements, and other market demands for agricultural products become more important. Traditional staples such as wheat or rice may pass through several intermediaries (harvesters, millers, wholesalers, retailers, and bakers) before reaching the consumer, with more value added at the food processing stage than at the production stage. New mass or modern markets may emerge, such as the animal feed market for corn and other markets. Each link in these “production-to-consumption” systems presents new opportunities for innovation.

Agricultural issues are changing along with changes in production. For example, poverty reduction can be achieved more quickly by creating jobs along the value chain than by increasing production. Food security concerns can have a greater impact on conservation management than on costs. Labor and water productivity may be no less important than land productivity. Public health threats such as avian influenza have led to major public interventions, which are more likely to be associated with famines or natural disasters. Other public health challenges include malnutrition and obesity. In developing and developed countries alike, the availability and affordability of food are no less important than the cost of food.

Traditional food sectors in developing countries are not immune to these changes. On the market side, corn uses include animal feed, starch, and additives such as fructose. Demand for dairy and meat products is growing very rapidly (often by 5 percent or more per year), driven by new hygiene and public health management requirements and product diversification (cheese, yogurt, yogurt drinks, cream, liquid milk, cold cuts, ready meals, and many other products). At first

glance, the rice and wheat sectors may seem less dynamic, but the focus on quality and the differentiation in production by use (e.g., cereals, bread) are increasing opportunities for innovation. In all cases, the transformation of traditional food sectors through marketing can also lead to strong changes on the production side. New approaches are needed to respond appropriately to the opportunities and threats of these transformation processes.¹

As the context of agricultural development has changed, so have the concepts of innovation, as well as the approaches to investing in it. In the 1980s, a “national agricultural research system” was developed to guide investment in agricultural development.

Strengthened research systems can increase the supply of new knowledge and technologies, but they do not necessarily improve the innovation process in the agricultural sector. In recent years, more attention has been paid to the demand for research and technology and to the development of broader competencies, linkages, incentive relationships, practices, governance structures and policies for the effective use of knowledge. An innovation system can include organizations, enterprises and individuals, as well as the relationships and rules between these different agents. The concept of innovation systems focuses not only on scientific providers, but also on all actors involved in the innovation process. This includes factors that influence the demand and use of new and existing knowledge, in addition to knowledge creation.

The concept of innovation systems offers interesting opportunities for how a country’s agricultural sector can better exploit new knowledge and develop alternative interventions that go beyond research investments. The concept is robust: its principles are derived from direct observations of countries and sectors with strong innovation track records – however, most of these observations have come from developed countries and the industrial sector. To date, the concept has been

¹ <https://www.worldbank.org/en/publication/wdr2020>

used mainly to explain past trends in economic performance. It has received less attention as a practical tool for analyzing the capacity to create and use knowledge in the sector and for designing interventions aimed at strengthening innovation capacity.

Traditionally, public policy and assistance, including assistance from the World Bank, have focused on building research and technology transfer systems and providing practical funding.

The question is, can the concept of innovation systems and the associated guidance on developing innovation capacity be translated into practical policies and projects to address practical challenges in agricultural development and sustainable economic growth? It assesses the usefulness of the concept of innovation systems in guiding investment in support of agricultural technology development and develops a practical concept of agricultural innovation systems for the Bank's client countries and partners. This article does not deny the importance of investing in research capacity, which is recognized as an essential element of innovation capacity in the concept of innovation systems. However, it focuses on the additional knowledge and types of interventions that can be added from an innovation systems perspective.

While staple food production remains crucial, the trend in many countries is the rapid development of new production-to-consumption systems in agriculture. Agricultural sectors around the world are increasingly expanding to include vegetables and fruits, spices, aquaculture products, and non-food products (e.g. medicinal plants); animal protein production is increasing; and the importance of processing and processing (often urban) is increasing to meet consumer demand for food safety and convenience. Although these new agricultural activities are highly variable, they often provide significant income and employment opportunities. Their development can make a significant contribution to sustainable development in rural areas.

Many new agricultural activities and products emerge as private entrepreneurs respond to new market opportunities. Often, the production and marketing efforts for these new products are very complex. Although the total cost of new agricultural activities can be large, the large number of products makes it impossible to develop each one for national research programs, except perhaps in very large countries, such as China and India. Therefore, countries will need to develop new approaches to support innovation in these knowledge-based activities. This “new agriculture” presents many relevant cases for developing practical frameworks based on the concept of innovation systems, as it describes a number of important new trends in the agricultural sectors of developing countries: (see Figure 1)

Figure 1. A number of important new trends in the agricultural sectors of developing countries²

-identification of new, dynamic and high-tech sectors, such as export horticulture and agrotechnology.

-rapidly changing consumer and marketing conditions.

² Mualliflar ishlanmasi

-industrialization of the food chain.

The need to compete in rapidly evolving international markets and the importance of innovation as a source of competitive advantage.

The need to upgrade and innovate in more traditional and old-tech sectors, such as agriculture, in new technology areas.

The need to adapt innovation capabilities to very diverse and changing conditions.

The development of agriculture is undergoing significant changes, these changes are closely related to science and technology, changing market dynamics and the increasing importance of innovation. However, with the rapid development of agricultural activities and the proliferation of new production-to-consumption systems, traditional approaches are no longer sufficient. The concept of innovation systems, focusing on the interactions between different activities and the integration of new knowledge, offers a framework for solving modern problems.

As agriculture becomes more integrated into global value chains and adapts to new market demands, the role of private enterprise, innovation and technology will become increasingly important. The shift to new, dynamic and knowledge-based sectors requires specific approaches beyond traditional research investments. By focusing on innovation systems, countries can better harness new knowledge, adapt to changing conditions and develop effective strategies for sustainable agricultural development.

In conclusion, the evolving agricultural landscape highlights the importance of diversification, new technologies, and new approaches to global markets. As new opportunities emerge, the need for a holistic approach to innovation increases. This approach, while supporting the development of new technologies, also takes into account the broader factors that influence the adoption and use of knowledge. In the future, policymakers, researchers, and stakeholders will need to adopt the principles

of innovation systems and develop effective strategies to increase agricultural productivity and sustain growth.

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